

LEARNING & TEACHING PROBLEMS FOR SPECIAL SKILL CERTIFICATE DISABLED STUDENT (KHK) FOR HK COURSE 206 WESTERN FOOD PREPARATION (HEARING IMPAIRED CATEGORY)

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Abstract

Students majoring in Certificate of Hotel & Catering Management in Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin Polytechnic, Perlis are disabled (Disabled People) with hearing impairment. They constitute a minority of students in Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin Polytechnic. The objective of this study is to help and find out the cause of the problems faced by disabled students, as well as suggestions on how to resolve the problems. This research is a quantitative research. Data was collected through questionnaires which were distributed during the class. The respondents were students of Hotel Management & Catering for semester 1 and 3, June 2013 session of the Department of Tourism and Hospitality. The results showed that the level of understanding and enjoyment of learning in the course is very low at 9%. Some of the proposed actions have been identified to improve student achievement in this subject.

Keywords: Disabled people , Students with hearing impairment

Research Reflection

People with auditory disabilities are special. They are unable to understand the speech from normal people. This defect is caused by lack of nutrition during the mother's pregnancy, high fever after the birth and has been involved in accidents.

(Nafiseh Alaghehband et al., 2013) stated that children with “special needs” refers to children with mental or physical disabilities which make a special situation involving personalized educational programs, services and essential care requirements. Designing special education programs to serve children with special health care requires exclusive materials, equipment and techniques of teaching in accordance with the capabilities of students.

Moreover, (Ainul, 2012) highlights the prevailing regulations and compliance standards found in Malaysian legal policies, such as the Person With Disabilities Act (PWDA 2008) (Part III of Act 685), which are aimed at facilitating the creation of accessibility to public facilities, amenities, services and equipment for PWDs. (Ainul, 2012) reiterates that accessibility is the key for PWDs to fully and effectively participate and contribute to the well-being and diversity of the community and society. (Roslinda et al., 2013) support also that the focus of the special education for the PWDs is on the physical, emotional, spiritual and intellectual development so that they can pursue their study at higher education, get a job and live independently.

Furthermore, (M. Rezaul Islam, 2015) stated that at the global level, the latest achievement is the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, the first legally binding disability-specific human rights convention; it is aimed at promoting, protecting and ensuring the full and equal enjoyment of all human rights and fundamental freedoms by PWDs.

Under (Section 28(1) of Persons with Disabilities Act 2008 (PWDA) provides for access to education that persons with disabilities shall not be excluded from the general education system on the basis of disabilities, and children with disabilities shall not be excluded from pre-school, primary, secondary and higher education, on equal basis with persons or children without disabilities, including vocational training and lifelong learning. Moreover, under subsection (2), the Government and private educational providers shall, in order to enable persons and children with disabilities to pursue education, provide reasonable accommodation suitable with the requirements of persons and children with disabilities in terms of, among others, infrastructure, equipment and teaching materials, teaching methods, curricula and other forms of support that meet the diverse needs of persons or children with disabilities. Besides their disabilities, the government gives an opportunity for them in the education, working and provides their legal rights.

Besides that, under (Section 36 of Education Act 1996, Malaysian Act) stated that a polytechnic established under paragraph 34(1)(c) may offer courses of study and training programmes approved by the Minister; and award certificates, diplomas or such other qualifications as may be prescribed. It shows that as one of the higher education in Malaysia, polytechnics also plays an important role to provide suitable education for students especially disable students. Furthermore, Minister to provide special education in special schools established under paragraph 34(1) or in

such primary or secondary schools as the Minister deems expedient (Section 40 of Education Act 1996).

The Minister also has power to prescribe the duration of and curriculum on special education as provided under Section 41 of the same Act, the Minister may by regulations prescribe the duration of primary and secondary education suitable to the needs of a pupil in receipt of special education; the curriculum to be used in respect of special education; the categories of pupils requiring special education and the methods appropriate for the education of pupils in each category of special schools; and any other matter which the Minister deems expedient or necessary for the purposes of this Chapter. We can say that the government concerns with the education for disable students as they gives the power to the Minister to prescribe the duration of and curriculum on special education.

(Supiah et al., 2014) mentioned that students with special educational needs (SEN), require a range of special support services in order to succeed in school. Typically, these services have been provided in specialized resource rooms or special education classes to meet individual needs of these students.

Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin Polytechnic, Perlis is the 18th polytechnic built by the Ministry of Higher Education. It began its operations in June, 2004, comprising 8 academic departments and one of them is the Department of Tourism and Hospitality. The department offers courses at certificate and diploma in Hotel and Catering as well as Tourism. Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin Polytechnic has been offering courses for certificate level in Hotel Management and Catering. It started the session in June 2011 and has now produced a total of approximately 50 students who have obtained certificates of recognition. Students are required to meet the 65 credit hours over four (4) semesters of 2 years during the study. There are theoretical and practical learning applied in this course which involves student participation in group or individual.

Disabled students are taught in the classroom by experienced lecturers. These lecturers are assisted by a translator whose role is to translate what he is trying to convey to the students. Restrictions often occur in the process of teaching and learning due to the barrier in communications between the lecturer and the students. Therefore, this indirectly causes the students to be unable to understand the topics in the syllabus of the course. This is due to the mental capacity level of auditory impaired students are different from others due to the lack of stimulation from the senses of hearing and speech which they experience. This view was supported by Woolfolk (1998), which confirms that information processing is a human mental activity which comprised of the process of receiving information, storing and producing it. These activities involve sensory memory that includes the senses of sight, hearing, taste, smell and touch. Based on the study, it has shown that 70% of the problems are caused by communication barrier and 30% is due to the teaching aids as well as the students themselves.

Observations were carried out in two classes; KHK 1 and KHK 2 session in June 2013 throughout the teaching and learning process. Researchers thought that the current teaching and learning system need to be improved and enhanced to cater the need of disabled students. Thus,

they could understand the contents of the subjects that will be learnt throughout the academic session in the institution better.

Research Focus

This study is conducted to identify the problems which arise during the learning process of the disabled students with hearing impairment for first and second semester certificate program of Hotel and Catering Department of Tourism and Hospitality Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin Polytechnic.

Objectives

General Objective

1. To identify the main problems faced by disabled students in the learning process of the subject in class.

Specific Objectives

1. To the problems that arises in the process of learning disabled students.
2. To overcome these learning problems.
3. To improve students' achievement in the certificate program of Hotel & Catering Management.

The target group

The target group consists of 34 disabled students of a total of 18 students from semester 1 and 16 more students are from semester 2 of the Hotel & Catering Management in Hospitality and Tourism Department of Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin Polytechnic.

Implementation of the study

In order to identify the real cause of problems in learning for disabled students, researchers have collected quantitative and qualitative data by distributing the questionnaires to the 34 students of KHK 1 and KHK 2. The results obtained are recorded in the form of tables, graphs and analysis for each question.

Survey

The questionnaire was carried out for 15 minutes for each student after theory session. The questionnaire was comprised of 20 questions. It was presented to each student. The questions raised were including of prerequisite knowledge on the topics that students have learnt, the problems encountered in the process of teaching and learning in the classroom. The questionnaire was translated into sign language and recorded by the researchers for collecting information purpose.

Problem Analysis Review

The sample used in the data analysis consisted of 34 students which is 38% boys and 62% girls. These students are 85% Malay, 9% Chinese, and 6% Indian, who were mainly aged between 21-22 years old, which were accounted for 64%, aged 19-20 years old were 24% while aged 23-24 years old were only 12%.

1.0 Questionnaire - Students

Figure 1- Analysis of Students

According to the analysis of data from the questionnaires, it has shown that 91% of the students as in Figure 1 above feel comfortable in classroom. The second highest is 85% which state students are reading notes while in the hostel. The other 76% stated they are eager to learn. Some 65% mentioned about the difficulty to remember and recall what have been taught by the lecturers. In addition, 53% confessed their weaknesses in terms of reading and writing. The other 50% said their weaknesses are in mastering sign language while the lowest score was 9% in which they expressed the boredom in the classroom.

These findings have shown that the students are interested in learning but hindered by inherent weaknesses.

2.0 Questionnaire - Students

Figure 2- The Content Syllabus

Based on the data analysis of the questionnaires in Figure 2, 94% of the samples agreed that they could understand short and simple sentences. The second highest score was 91%. It shows that these students prefer to learn visually in which they like more pictures and graphics while learning whereas 62% said they were unable to understand the long, complicated sentences. The lowest score of 41% specified that the contents of the syllabus of the teaching are appropriate. All of these findings have indicated that the content of the syllabus need to be improved to suit and cater the needs of disabled students.

3.0 Questionnaire – Performance/Achievement in the Classroom

Figure 3- Analysis of Performance in class

Section C: Analysis of Achievement Inside

Analysis of data from the questionnaires has found that students as in Figure 3 above shows the highest score is 91% in which stating that students understand what is taught in the classroom. The second highest score was 85%; students are able to answer questions by the lecturers well. Meanwhile, the other 71% stated that they always submit the assignments on time. Apart of that, 65% claimed they normally pass the quizzes and exams taken. The lowest score was 41%; students often copy friends' assignments in order to complete the task.

These findings have suggested that teaching sessions conducted by lecturers are top-notch quality and satisfying.

4.0 Questionnaire - Learning Aid / Visual Aid

Figure 4- Analysis of Teaching Aid

Section D: Teaching Aid Analysis

According to the data analysis from the questionnaires, it has shown that the highest score is 94% which is students are in favor of attractive and colourful graphics. The second highest score was 91% indicated that videos and power point presentations ease the students to learn in the classroom. Moreover, 88% stated that they could achieve better understanding in learning by looking at eye-catching figures. The lowest score is 59% has stated that the privations of appropriate reference books are available in the library.

These have indicated that the students mostly are visual learners as they prefer to learn by inculcation of more images and videos in teaching and learning process.

5.0 Item Analysis

Figure 5 - Mean Analysis for All Items

Mean analysis from the survey shows it was clearly stated that the highest mean score was for the items of teaching aids namely by 83%. This indicates that majority of the students need teaching aids in the form of pictures or videos to provide more stimulus and enrich as well as develop their understanding in learning.

Actions Taken to Overcome the Problems

Based on the analysis, the mastery level of the disabled from HK 206 course on western cuisine preparation is weak. Among the factors contributing to the occurrence of this problem is the lack of understanding of the students for some of the topics and the ability to master the knowledge and skills learnt. Researchers found that lack of speech and auditory senses also contribute to the problem of memorizing among respondents.

Hearing impaired students rely heavily on sign language as compared with normal group using normal spoken language. Language gap is also one of the factors to the prayer recitation problems faced by the students. According to Chua and Koh (1992), hearing impaired students in schools in Malaysia learn pertaining to standard curriculum that has been catered to their needs and ability. Six years in primary school and five years in secondary school are compulsory for every student. However, two additional years is added for students with hearing problems.

From the above analysis, the researcher will carry out actions to resolve the issues. The proposed actions are as follows:

- 1) Developing interactive video CD to assist in the process of teaching and learning course especially for HK 206.
- 2) Preparing written reports and contents improvement of HK 206 syllabus.
- 3) Focusing on topics that require high skills for the disabled that are weak in study.

The proposed actions will be covering the entire topics in the HK 206 course and not only involves the participation of students and lecturers directly in the form of practical. The learning process is not only will be lecturer-centred but also focussing on active learning for students in order to master the knowledge. The researchers believe that students' involvement in hands-on and minds-on will stimulate their long-term memory. This is consistent with the opinion of Rohizani, Mohd Shahabuddin and Zohir (2005), which affirmed that the teaching skills should be emphasized on the instruction, demonstration and correction. Moreover, according to Abdul Raof (1998), the combination of a variety of activities that involve teaching strategies, approaches, methods and techniques will lead to effective teaching. On top of that, Fani Bari, Manisah Ali, Norani Mohd and Aliza Alias (2002) states that a child with hearing problems is synonymous with communication problems, social as well as academic. Thus, the repetition of the topics should be done reiteratively to ensure that they master the topics learnt better.

Implementation and Observation

The action was carried out in six weeks whereas the observation of the results was done for a week to students.

Action (1) was carried out by the lecturers during the process of teaching and learning in the classroom for two weeks in a row. The lecturer took 1 hour to show video of cooking utensils and cuisine. He repeated it several times to strengthen the students' memory.

Action (2) was carried out during a meeting for drafting the curriculum at the Polytechnic Department. The content of the syllabus will be revised according to the skills and capabilities of the disabled students.

Action (3) shall be implemented during the course of HK 206 for 2 weeks. Lecturers will focus on the disabled students who are weak by providing intensive tutoring. Mentor mentee concept will be emphasized throughout the class.

Suggestion for Further Study

There are some follow-up action researches that can be carried out in respect of student with disabilities in teaching and learning process such as studies on the effectiveness of the multimedia usage among the disabled students. There are few websites such as Facebook, Edmodo and others where lecturers can easily share information on subject matter with disabled students in the internet.

Last but not least, further study on the perception of lecturers who teach disabled students with hearing categories is needed. This research is necessary as to identify the problems faced by the lecturers during the process of teaching and learning in the classroom. It can also be considered as an enhancement of skills of the lecturers involved.

References

- Nafiseh Alagheband Ghadim, Norlidah Alias, Syar Meeze Mohd Rashid and Mohd Yakub Zulkifli Bin Mohd Yusoff.(2013), “Mother’s Perspective Toward al-Quran Education for Hearing Impaired Children in Malaysia”, Retrieved from <http://www.mojet.net/volume/mojet-volume01-issue04.pdf#page=32> on 23rd January 2015
- Ainul, J.M. (2012), “Legal framework regulating for improving accessibility to build environment for disabled persons in Malaysia”, Retrieved from <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1992205> on 23rd January 2015
- M. Rezaul Islam. (2015), “Rights of the People with Disabilities and Social Exclusion in Malaysia”,International Journal of Social Science and Humanity, Vol. 5, No. 2, February 2015, Retrieved from <http://www.ijssh.org/papers/447-H10019.pdf> on 2nd March 2015
- Roslinda Alias, Nor Aziah Alias, Abu Bakar Ibrahim, Halimaton Attand and Azman L Kadire. (2013),” What Do the Disabled Students Need? A Study on the Needs of the Special Educational Needs (SEN) Learners in Malaysian Public Universities”, The European Journal of Social & Behavioural Sciences (eISSN: 2301-2218),Retrieved from http://www.c-crscs.com/files/menu_items/other/ejsbs37.pdf on 24th January 2015.
- Nafiseh Alagheband Ghadim, Norlidah Alias, Syar Meeze Mohd Rashid and Mohd Yakub Zulkifli Bin Mohd Yusoff.(2013), “Mother’s Perspective Toward al-Quran Education for Hearing Impaired Children in Malaysia”, Retrieved from <http://www.mojet.net/volume/mojet-volume01-issue04.pdf#page=32> on 23rd January 2015
- Safani Bari, Manisah Ali, Norani Mohd, & Aliza Alias. (2002). *Penggunaan alat bantuan pendengaran di kalangan murid-murid bermasalah pendengaran*. Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.
- Chua T. T., & Koh, B.B. (1992). *Pendidikan khas dan pemulihan*. Kuala Lumpur: Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka Rohizani
- Yaakub, Shahabudin Hashim, & Mohd Zohir Ahmad. (2005). *Pedagogi: Strategi dan teknik mengajar dengan berkesan*. Bentong: PTS Publications & Distributors Sdn. Bhd.
- Woolfolk, A.E. (1998). *Educational Psychology*. (7th ed.). Boston: Allyn & Bacon Wayne
- Gisslen (2011)Professional Cooking (7th ed)